

Using Spiral Notch Torsion Test to Evaluate Fracture Toughness of Fiber-Reinforced Polymeric Composites

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Abstract

This paper studied the fracture behavior of fiber-reinforced composites using the spiral notch torsion test. Cylindrical specimens of fiber-reinforced polymeric composites with spiral notches were fabricated along different orientations with respect to the fiber orientation. The critical loads upon failure under monotonic torsion were recorded at different loading rates. Fractographic characterization revealed novel failure patterns in the fiber-epoxy interfaces, including fiber-matrix delamination and alternative inter- and intra- circular cracks. By incorporating the mechanical properties of the fiber composites, finite element modeling was successfully applied to characterize the effect of material anisotropy on the stress contour around the crack tip for different specimens.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

It is difficult to measure the strict plane-strain fracture toughness of structural materials based on the ASTM standard test method (E399) [1], since the target materials may be geometrically unsuitable or volumetrically limited to be fabricated into standard specimens. Therefore, it is beneficial to use small specimens to obtain K_{IC} data in many applications [2]. If consistent K_{IC} values could be directly measured, the safety margins associated with current regulations

on the assessment of material properties will be improved substantially. Furthermore, for statistically inhomogeneous materials, it will require a large number of testing samples having a long crack front to obtain a statistical mean value of fracture toughness. The amount and size of these requirements may not be practical for many materials of interest.

1.2 Specimen size effect

Significant effort has been applied to develop experimental techniques to study the fracture behavior with small specimens; few methods could directly measure K_{IC} without a concern of the size effect. Meanwhile, failure of real structure seldom occurs in a single mode, such as mode I in pure tension. For example, wind turbine systems are subject to a complex combination of stress status, especially to the turbine blades in rotation. Some component design are effective in mitigating flexural loading (mode I: tensile failure), they may not be efficient enough in resisting the torsional load (mode III: the out-of-plane shear failure). Fracture behavior under mixed mode loading (modes I and III) is not well known, partially due to the experimental difficulties with the test method using a compact-tension specimen.

2 Spiral Notch Torsion Test

2.1 Test description

A new method, Spiral Notch Torsion Test (SNTT), was developed to study the fracture behavior using cylindrical specimen for different structural materials [2], as will be detailed in the following sections.

The SNTT test method applied torsion to a cylindrical specimen having a V-grooved spiral line with a 45° pitch (Fig. 1). When the grooved specimen is sectioned into segments perpendicular to the groove line, each tiny segment can be viewed as a notched Compact-Tension (CT) specimen. Therefore all the virtual CT specimens are bonded together side-by-side, the compatibility condition [2] is automatically satisfied, remaining in place before and after application of torsion loading. In the square element with shear stresses (Fig. 1), the principal stresses are aligned with the red arrows (in tension) and white arrows (in compression). When a notch is introduced, a tri-axial tensile stress field will evolve in around the notch root area. This observation has been experimentally and analytically validated in previous study [2].

General consensus has been raised to support the method using compact-tension specimens as a standard method, some deficiencies to meet the requirements of the classical theory of fracture mechanics remain for such conventional approaches. The SNTT test system operates by applying pure torsion to cylindrical specimens having a spiral notch line around the specimen at a 45° pitch angle. The pure torsion creates a uniform equi-biaxial tension/compression stress field along the concentric segments. The grooved line effectively becomes a Mode I crack opening in tensile failure. It is reasonable to visualize that the cylindrical specimen as a transformed manifestation of a compact-tension specimen having a width equivalent to the total length of the spiral notch. However, it is difficult to uniformly distribute the applied loads through the entire thickness of the conventional compact-tension specimens. This is because the stresses at and near the

two free surfaces are anomalous, resulting in shear lip formation often discernible in fractured specimens. In contrast, the torque load acting on every cross-section along the cylindrical specimen is identical. A plane-strain condition is successfully achieved on every plane orthogonal to the spiral groove.

2.2 Deformation of the SNTT configuration

Because of the plane-strain, axisymmetric constraint and the uniformity in the stress and strain fields of SNTT configuration, the crack front must propagate perpendicularly towards the specimen axis. A specimen with intrinsic symmetry to study the fracture of materials is established. Due to the 3-D non-coplanar crack front of SNTT configuration and the lack of close form solutions, K_{IC} of SNTT method was evaluated using 3-D finite element analysis with J-Integral based on domain integral method [3].

2.3 Mixed-mode fracture toughness

Li *et al.* [4] developed an experimental set-up using a specially machined steel CT specimen. Their results indicate that mixed mode I-III toughness and tearing modulus reduced to 50% and 30%, respectively, compared to those under Mode I for some ductile materials. Therefore, the synergistic impact due to the combination of flexural normal stress (Mode I fracture) and the torsion shear stress (Mode III fracture) to the fracture performance of the materials need a further review, especially in systems subject to rotating loading. As for the brittle materials, the Mode I is still the dominate failure mode, such as for epoxy materials. The mixed mode I-III study could be performed by varying the spiral notch pitch angle away from the 45° to other angles.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Materials

The composite SNTT specimens used in this study were fabricated from composite plates made from the vacuum assisted infusion technique (Fig. 2). These plates consisted of 20 layers of unidirectional fabrics

stitched at 90° (E-LT 5500-10, Vectorply Corp. Phenix City, AL). The infused epoxy was Epikote RIMR 135 resin/Epikure RIMH1366 curing agent (Momentive, Columbus, OH). The resin to curing agent weight ratio was 100:30, while the plates were cured at 70°C for 8 h for completion. The fabrication of the fiber-reinforced composites used in this study is shown in Fig.2.

Fiber-reinforced composites are anisotropic materials. It is important to characterize the materials properties along different orientations, because these properties could affect the crack growth pattern along these directions. In this study, the fiber-reinforced polymeric composites were treated as orthotropic materials. The corresponding mechanical properties, including the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio, are measured experimentally along different orientations [5]. The details of the data are summarized in Table 1.

3.2. Specimens

Three types of SNTT specimens were fabricated along different orientation, including (1) type A: the cylinder axis is perpendicular to fiber orientation; (2) type B: the cylinder axis is parallel to fibers; and (3) type C: the cylinder axis is at 45° to fiber orientation. The detail views of the spiral notch in different specimens are shown in Fig.3. The diameter of the cylinder was 1.0 cm, and the notch depth was 0.2 cm.

3.3. Experimental methods

A servo-hydraulic axial-torsional testing machine (Model 809, MTS Systems Corp. Eden Prairie, MN, USA) was used to perform testing of composite SNTT specimens. The experiment set-up is shown in Fig.4. Metallic fixtures were designed to adapt to the components of MTS machine. Both ends were inserted to the fixtures (Fig. 4b) to stabilize the specimen before testing [6]. In order to evaluate the effect of loading rate the critical failure load to the specimens, three different loading rates were selected

to perform a series of test, including 0.56, 1.13 and 2.26 N-m/sec (5, 10 and 20 in-lbf/sec). Three replicates were collected for each specimen to generate statistical data.

In order to apply pure torsion to specimens, the axial loading force during the test was controlled to minimum. Thus, the axial force for testing series of 0.56 and 2.26 N-m/sec were 2.2 N; whereas the one for 1.13 N-m were 22.2 N.

4. Finite element modeling

A finite element model was established in ABAQUS™ [3] for the composite SNTT sample. Due to the rotational symmetry of the helix structure, part of the cylindrical sample was modeled from the entire specimen. The crack tip area was meshed with wedge elements C3D15. The rest of the areas were meshed with elements C3020R. Finer mesh was established around the crack tip, while coarser mesh was distributed for the rest area. A smooth transition was achieved between the coarse and fine meshes. In the finite element model, a concentrated torque was applied at the center of the cross section on one end of the cylinder model. On the other end, the in-plane translations were fixed to simulate the necessary constraints for the specimen. The total mesh is shown in Fig. 5a.

All materials used in this study were assumed as orthotropic materials. The primary materials properties used in this study were based on the experimental measurement summarized in Table 1.

5. Results

5.1 Load-displacement curves

Representative loading curves of the SNTT test for different types of specimens are shown in Fig.6. The characteristic in three types of specimen were clearly presented. For all three specimens, a well-defined linear curve existed in the beginning of the curves.

However, the post-peak behavior varied substantially from different types of specimen.

In type A specimen, the peak torque was lowest among those of all three specimens, and the load dropped significantly after the peak. Several failure stairs appeared before the torque decreased to minimum. In type B specimen, the peak torque was the highest among those of the three. But the peak load remained at the same level as with a saw tooth shape variation before a slight decreasing occurred. In the type C specimen, the peak load was in between that of type A and B, and a quick drop after the peak load also appeared in post-peak step failures.

5.2 Effect of loading rates

Based on the three loading rates applied in this study, i.e., 0.56, 1.13 and 2.26 N-m/sec, the critical failure loads were collected for each specimen (Fig.7). For each loading rate, the type B specimen exhibited the highest peak load; while the type A specimen exhibited the lowest peak load. The peak load of type C specimen was in between those of type A and type B. Based on the data in Fig.7, the peak loads for each type of specimen were not sensitive to the loading rates selected in the study.

5.3 Fractographic characterization

The fracture surfaces of the failed specimens were examined using both optical images and Scanning Electron Microscopes (S-3400, Hitachi, Japan).

5.3.1 Type A specimen

The type A specimen split into two halves after failure. Both fiber and strand failures could be observed in Fig.8a. The SEM image (Fig. 8b) showed that the cracks propagated along the interface between the fiber and the epoxy, while the glass fibers remained intact. Shear deformation lines could also be detected along the fiber-matrix interface, a clear evidence of the shearing stress under the torsional loading. Since the fiber orientation was orthogonal to the cylinder axis, the cracks could propagate through the entire fiber length upon failure.

5.3.2 Type B specimen

The type B specimen did not split into halves upon failure. Based on the front and back view of the failed specimen (Fig. 9a), there were white failure zone around spiral notch area. In order to further characterize failure details, a cross section view was obtained by cutting along the center of the specimen (Fig. 9b). Different types of crack were detected, including the cracks between fabric layers, crack between fiber strands and a circular crack. The circular crack starting from notch tip propagated around the unnotched area with alternative inter- to intra- crack growth patterns.

5.3.3 Type C specimen

The type C specimen also split into two halves after failure. Instead of a straight cutting step surface in Fig.8a, the fracture surface exhibited a curvature (Fig.10). This was due to the 45° angle between fiber direction and the cylinder axis.

5.4 Finite element results

Finite element analysis was performed to characterize the fracture behavior of different types of specimens under torsion. The von Mises stress distributions of a representative deformed type specimen was shown in Fig.11a with a scale factor of 20. It exhibited that stress concentration occurred around the spiral notch of the cylinder. Similar stress concentrations around the notch were also found for deformed type A and C specimens.

Meanwhile, the stress contours around the crack tip were also plotted for further analysis in Figs 11b-11d. Different stress contours were observed in type A, B and C specimens. In type A specimen, the fiber orientation was perpendicular to the cylinder axis with a length of the cylindrical diameter. So the specimen could split into halves after failure. In type B specimens, the fibers were parallel to the cylindrical axis with the same length as the specimen. Even though delamination occurred upon failure, the

fibers could still hold the failed piece together. In type C specimen, the fibers were 45° with the cylindrical orientation with a length between that of type A and B.

The mechanical property along the fiber orientation is significantly different from those in the trans-fiber and stacking orientations (Table 1). In type A specimen, the unsymmetrical stress contour around the crack tip is a proof of this material anisotropy (Fig. 11b). The stress level was also lowest in type A specimen. However, in type B specimen, the mechanical properties in the trans-fiber and the stacking orientations were similar to each other, the stress contour were relatively symmetric (Fig 11c). In type C specimen, both the shape and stress level around the crack tip was in between those of type A and type B specimens (Fig. 11d).

6. Conclusions

In this paper, the fracture behavior of fiber-reinforced polymeric composites was studied using spiral notch torsion test. Three types of composite specimens were fabricated from unidirectional laminate composites. The angle between the specimen axis and the fiber orientation were 90° in type A specimen, 0° in type B specimen, and 45° in type C specimen. Type A specimen split into halves upon failure, and interfacial failure between glass fibers and epoxy were observed. Type B specimen remained together even though delamination occurred around the spiral notch. Fractographic analysis revealed the presence of three types of cracks, including the interfacial fiber layer crack, fiber strand crack and a circular crack around the unnotched area. Type C specimen also split into halves but with a curved fracture surface.

In finite element analysis, effect of orthotropy on the fracture was displayed by von Mises stress contour around the crack tip in different types of composite specimens. Type A specimen exhibited the lowest stress level, and the unsymmetrical stress

contour was attributed to significant difference of mechanical properties between the fiber and the other two orientations. Type B specimen exhibited the highest stress level, and the stress contour was relatively symmetric due to the similar mechanical properties between the stacking and the trans-fiber orientations. Type C specimen exhibited the intermediate stress level and the stress contour shape between those of type A and B.

Acknowledgments

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Fig 1. A schematic of Spiral Notch Torsion Test

Fig.2. An image showing the fabrication of the fiber-reinforced polymeric composites using vacuum assisted infusion techniques.

Type A Specimen

Type B Specimen

Fig.3 (a) Three types of SNTT specimens used in this study, including type A, type B and type C specimens with different fiber orientation; Optical images with higher resolution (b) type A specimen; (c) type B specimen and (d) type C specimens.

Fig.5. (a) The mesh of finite element model used in the study; material models (b) type A specimen; (c) type B specimen and (d) type C specimen.

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Table 1. Mechanical properties of the fiber reinforced composites.

Orthotropic Material Properties			
E_1 (GPa)	44.60	G_{23} (GPa)	3.77
E_2 (GPa)	17.00	ν_{12}	0.262
E_3 (GPa)	16.70	ν_{23}	0.350
G_{12} (GPa)	3.49	ν_{13}	0.264
G_{23} (GPa)	3.46	ρ (kg/m ³)	1924